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INTEGRATING CARE IN A COMMUNITY MENTAL HEALTH CENTER:
A CASE STUDY

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

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By

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ABSTRACT

Historically, treatment for serious mental illness (SMI) has been separated from the rest of medicine resulting in gaps in medical care, redundant care, and increased costs. To address the healthcare needs of those with SMI, primary care services are now being embedded in and connected to community mental health centers (CMHCs). The purpose of this project was to describe and analyze the system changes that occurred in a nationally recognized CMHC's grant-funded initiatives to integrate primary and behavioral healthcare into its repertoire of services for persons with SMI. Grant outcomes included increasing the number of persons with SMI who were connected with a primary care provider (PCP) in the local community and those who have active insurance. These outcomes were successful, as nearly three-quarters of the previously uninsured members became connected with public insurance, and 122 members were connected with a community PCP. Other deliverables designed to increase the level of integration at the CMHC encountered barriers, such as staff resistance, EHR challenges, philosophical differences, and the need for program re-design and highlighted the lack of coordination between agencies. This case study suggests that efforts to provide integrated care in a CMHC may necessitate an organizational culture shift that includes the active, cohesive, and clear support of leadership. In addition, strong theoretical underpinnings are necessary to support the change. Prochaska and DiClemente's stages of change (1982) and Roger's Diffusion of Innovations (1962) are examples of theories that can help organizations to successfully adapt to a fully integrated care system.

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INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND

This project was designed to address the inadequate medical care being received by persons with serious and persistent mental illness (SMI). This project provides a background to the problem and presents a review of the literature with pertinent themes and topic areas. Additionally, to provide further context and rationale for the project, relevant conceptual frameworks are discussed. Beyond this, the aims and goals of the project are presented with associated methods, results, discussion, and recommendations.

In a local behavioral health treatment facility, an endeavor to address medical and behavioral health integration for their clients (called members by the facility) was attempted by applying for two grants to fund physical health screening and interventions. The lack of evidence for effective medical and behavioral health integration among SMI individuals created problems in deploying envisioned grant activities. .

Problem Statement

Historically, mental health and addiction treatment have been separated from all other kinds of medicine (Barry & Huskamp, 2011). This fragmentation in the healthcare system has led to gaps in care; inappropriate, disjointed, and redundant care; and increased healthcare costs (Kaiser Commission on Medicaid and the Uninsured, 2014). The lack of integrated mental health and physical health services may account for the health disparities suffered by the mentally ill, resulting in calls for integrated care. The National Council for Community Behavioral Healthcare (NCCBH) noted that the “gap between medical and behavioral healthcare systems must be bridged” (2003, p. 1).

Nationwide, many state agencies, health plans, and provider systems are currently implementing medical and behavioral health integration strategies to bridge the gaps

between primary healthcare and behavioral healthcare (Kaiser Commission on Medicaid and the Uninsured, 2014). Some form of integration is considered the best path to enhance and improve quality of care, quality of life, and access to care, and to reduce costs (CalMEND, 2011). Yet, to date, very little evidence is available regarding effective and sustainable medical and behavioral health integration strategies for persons with SMI (Barry & Huskamp, 2011).

Project Aim

The purpose of the initiative supported by two grants was to increase the level of integration of services by incorporating physical healthcare screening and measures into a behavioral health treatment facility that serves persons with SMI living in the community. More specifically, the intention was to create a structure (system change) that adapted the existing function of the treatment team to focus more on the integration of mental health and physical healthcare for members receiving mental health treatment at a Californian CMHC. The goal was to improve the percentage of members receiving supportive treatment for designated health conditions and evaluate the culture related to integrating primary care measures into a CMHC.

The aim of this doctoral project was to describe and analyze the system changes in various community and health system arenas resulting from implementing the initiative to integrate physical and mental health care. The CMHC received two grants to improve and refine the efforts to integrate care at the CMHC. The aims of this doctoral project were coordinated with the Patient Protection and the Affordable Care Act (ACA) of 2010, the *Integrated Healthcare Project* grant provided by the California Community Foundation, and the *Access to Physical Health Care for People with Serious Mental*

Illness grant provided by the Robert Ellis Simon Foundation. The expected outcomes of the grants included adapting the mental health agency's practices to identify physical healthcare problems among its members, support client navigation of complex healthcare systems, and coordinate mental health and physical care delivery.

This project examined the implementation efforts in order to develop and determine the appropriate next steps and improve future efforts of care integration. More specifically, the aim of this project was to analyze and evaluate the various efforts of the CMHC to provide more integrated care to its members. This analysis and evaluation aimed to provide substantive information to guide further efforts of the CMHC and clarify barriers and challenges not only to the CMHC and mental health agency but also to the broader audience of other CMHCs striving to provide quality integrated care.

Description of the CMHC and the Grant Initiatives

This project was conducted at a Southern Californian CMHC that provides services to SMI individuals living in its local community. The staffing at the CMHC includes nurses, case managers, nurse practitioners, psychiatrists, and various clerical and administrative staff. The organization sought, by means of the *Integrated Healthcare Project* grant, to embed a medical assistant and primary care nurse practitioner in the CMHC two mornings per week to provide medical care. The measurable objectives of the grant are as follows:

- conduct physical assessments and provide short-term primary care (average of 2– 4 visits) and education to 125 individuals with mental illness by embedding a part-time nurse practitioner at the CMHC,

- connect or re-connect 100 eligible individuals to a public insurance/managed Medi-Cal provider to ensure ongoing access to care,
- collaborate with the physical healthcare provider to integrate physical and mental health treatment and medication issues for 125 individuals with multiple needs.

The *Access to Physical Health Care for People with Serious Mental Illness* grant included numerous specific deliverables. These included determining and implementing changes in a pilot project targeting one specific treatment team. Additionally, the deliverables included the creation of a health screening form and registry; a companion document, named “My Medical Visit” form; a newly designed Community Health Resource Guide; and staff training on all new materials.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

There are various ways to conceptualize and practice integrating care. Models, methods, and best practices for integrating care have been conceptualized and implemented utilizing the guidance of various conceptual frameworks. This project employed conceptual frameworks to guide its foundation, structure, and process. According to Polit and Beck (2012), a conceptual framework can “provide a perspective regarding interrelated phenomena” (p. 128). Additionally, a conceptual framework can present a visual representation that can be effective in “expressing abstract ideas in a concise and convenient form” (Polit & Beck, 2012, p. 128).

The overarching theory supporting this project, and at the root of collaborative and integrated care, is the biopsychosocial theory developed by Engel (1977). The understanding of mind and body interrelation is not a new concept. Generally stated, this theory acknowledges that, “biological, psychological, and social factors all play a significant role in human functioning in the context of disease” (Engel as cited by Collins et al., 2010, p. 6).

Two conceptual models were used to frame the scope, nature, and rationale for the project’s aims and efforts made to integrate physical healthcare measures. The models also assist in the consideration of population and systemic changes and responses, and direct the efforts to transform healthcare systems from reactive systems into proactive, integrated systems.

The Four Quadrant Clinical Integration Model

The first model, the Four Quadrant Clinical Integration Model, is a conceptual framework for population-based planning developed by the National Council for

Community Behavioral Healthcare (NCCBH) (Parks & Pollack, 2005). This model serves to define the population in need of services and provides organizational models of integration related to the differing needs of the population in each quadrant.

The Four Quadrant Clinical Integration Model's foundation is rooted in a 1998 consensus document intended to foster integration for mental health and substance abuse/addiction services. The preliminary document, which was conceived by state mental health and substance abuse directors (National Association of State Mental Health Program Directors [NASMHPD] and the National Association of State Alcohol/Drug Abuse Directors [NASADAD]), was further developed by Ken Minkoff and associates (Parks & Pollack, 2005).

The model initially served to delineate the relationship between the risk/complexity of mental health and substance abuse/addiction and "the clinical competency in mental health and substance abuse/addiction knowledge and skills within the service provided" (Parks & Pollack, 2005, p. 11). The model has been amended to consider the behavioral health and physical health risks and complexity of each quadrant's population subset. Furthermore, the model aims to identify major elements of the system to utilize in order to meet the needs of the individuals within each quadrant's subset of the population (Parks & Pollack, 2005, p. 11). According to the Substance Abuse and Mental Health Services Administration [SAMHSA] and the Health Resources and Services Administration's [HRSA] Center for Integrated Health Solutions [CIHS], the four quadrant model is a popular and generally accepted way to measure a facility's level of integration (SAMHSA-HRSA CIHS, n.d.).

The four quadrants of the model describe the population to be served, the different levels of Behavioral Health/Primary Care integration, and the clinical competencies divided into severity for each area of care (Amujahid, 2013). In this visual model, the horizontal axis represents the physical health risk or status of the individual receiving treatment. The vertical axis represents the behavioral health risk or status of the individual. Each axis represents the continuum range from low risk and complexity to high risk and complexity (see Figure 1).

Individuals categorized into quadrant I and quadrant III are deemed by the model to have low behavioral health risk and/or status. These individuals are not considered to be actively challenged with SMI (NCCBH, 2003). This project focused on individuals in quadrants II and IV, as these quadrants address those persons with high behavioral health needs, indicating an active SMI/issue. Therefore, this project focused on persons with SMI who have either a low physical healthcare risk/complexity or a high physical healthcare risk/complexity.

Figure 1. The Four Quadrant Clinical Integration Model. Adapted from *Behavioral health/primary care integration models, competencies, and infrastructure*. National Council for Community Behavioral Healthcare, 2003. Retrieved from Integrated Behavioral Health website: <http://www.ibhp.org/uploads/file/Mauers%20Behav%20Health%20Models%20Competencies%20Infra.pdf>

The Chronic Care Model

The second conceptual model underpinning this project is an adaptation of the Chronic Care Model (CCM). The CCM was developed in the 1990s by Ed Wagner, MD, MPH, Director of the MacColl Institute for Healthcare Innovation, Group Cooperative of

Puget Sound, and his colleagues of the Improving Chronic Illness Care Program with the support of the Robert Wood Johnson Foundation (Wagner, 1998). The model was tested nationally in 1998 across a variety of healthcare settings resulting in the adoption of the national program, “Improving Chronic Illness Care” (Wagner et al., 2001). The model has since been used in various settings such as community health center initiatives, the 2002 Assertive Community Treatment (ACT) Report, and the highly effective TEAMcare study (Katon et al., 2010). The model was further refined in 2003 (Improving Chronic Illness Care, 2014a). In California, nine public hospital systems came together in 2004–2005 for the Chronic Care Learning Communities Initiative under the aim of working to transform care for diabetic patients under the CCM (Improving Chronic Illness Care, 2014b). The CCM has also been implemented by a large number of healthcare organizations in the United States (US), the United Kingdom, and Sweden (Barr et al., 2003). Additionally, international versions of the CCM have been used in Canada, Denmark, Russia, China, Australia, and New Zealand (Improving Chronic Illness Care, 2014b). While the CCM can be applied to a wide range of chronic illnesses, healthcare settings, and target populations, the end result of the model aims to develop healthier patients and more satisfied providers, and to save costs.

The CCM has been expanded through an initiative by the California Department of Healthcare Services, the California Department of Mental Health, and the California Institute for Mental Health. Developments of this initiative have adopted a modified CCM that includes core values related to integration including person-centered, recovery-based, wellness-focused, family, cultural inclusion, and cultural humility (CalMEND, 2011). The Milbank report, “Evolving Models of Behavioral Health Integration in

Primary Care,” noted current and evolving integration models, which are consistent with the core values included by the California Department of Healthcare Services, California Department of Mental Health, and California Institute for Mental Health initiative in this revised model (Collins et al., 2010). The core constructs of the CCM are designed to work synergistically to produce the intended and improved outcomes.

Figure 2. The CCM. Adapted from *Integration of mental health, substance use, and primary care services* (Volume 1) by CalMEND, 2011. Retrieved from http://www.integration.samhsa.gov/sliders/slider_10.3.pdf

Constructs of the CCM

The major constructs of the CCM are defined (Improving Chronic Illness Care, 2014c) as follows:

Community (Resources & Policies). The role of community programs is to support and enhance care for its members and the health systems awareness, use, and partnership with these community organizations to reduce duplication of efforts and identify and fill gaps in service needs. The aim is to mobilize community resources to meet the needs of patients.

Health systems (Health Care Organizations). A system that promotes safe, high quality care, and care coordination through its culture and organization. Related concepts may include the need for comprehensive system change, effective improvement strategies, prevention of errors, instalment of quality measures to improve care, and data-sharing among facilities and providers.

Four key constructs fall under the umbrella of the Health System:

Clinical Information Systems. The organization of both patient and population data in a coordinated and effective way that facilitates efficient and effective care and enhances performance monitoring and quality improvement efforts (Improving Chronic Illness Care, 2014c).

Decision Support. The provision of clinical care consistent with evidence-based practice guidelines and patient preferences. This may include the use of proven education methods to educate patients about evidence-based guidelines and the integration of specialist expertise and primary care.

Delivery System Design. the design of the healthcare system that ensures effective, efficient clinical care, and encourages self-management support. Among these elements are health literacy, cultural sensitivity, definition of roles and distribution of tasks, clinical case management for more complex patients, and the practice of evidence-based care.

Self-management Support. Recognizing the central role patients have in their care and fostering a sense of responsibility for their health. The aim is to empower and prepare patients to manage their health and healthcare. Issues central to this aim include organizing internal system and community resources to support a patient's self-management. This can be achieved through collaborative approaches, establishing mutually agreed upon goals and treatment plans, and providing health information and emotional support.

The above elements are intended to work in conjunction and form the basis for productive interactions between caregivers and care receivers. Productive interactions are intended to be timely and efficient, coordinated, evidence-based, safe, and based on a person-centered approach. This CCM postulates that the combination of community and health system elements provided through productive interactions will produce three powerful outcomes: (a) informed and empowered patients and families, (b) a proactive and prepared practice team, and (c) improved health outcomes for individuals and populations (Improving Chronic Illness Care, 2014c).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Overview

For this project, a literature review was conducted. The databases searched were PubMed, CINAHL, EBSCO, Google Scholar, Google, OVID, and Cochrane Reviews. The databases were accessed via Polack library at California State University, Fullerton, with access via the Southern California, California State University Doctor of Nursing Consortium. The timeframe searched was January 2000–October 2014. Sentinel articles published before this timeframe were also included. The key words used in the search were “mental health,” “physical health,” “integrated care,” “health needs,” “serious mental illness (SMI),” “co-location,” “comprehensive care (within psychiatric care),” “medical care of SMI,” “medical conditions of SMI,” “co-morbidities of SMI,” “medical case-management of SMI,” “improved physical health outcomes of SMI,” and “models of integrated care.” Literature searches were conducted during the course of this project to search for and review relevant newly published studies.

Articles discussing the management of physical health needs of the seriously mentally ill and detailing models of integration, specifically integrating medical care into a behavioral health community setting, were included. Exclusion criteria included articles dealing only with clients whose mental health problems are secondary to medical problems or caused by the loss of a loved one, articles dealing exclusively with systems of care outside the US, articles that assumed integrated care means inclusion of complementary therapies in regular medical care, and articles not published in English.

Life Span of the Mentally Ill

Mental illness affects one in four people, which equates to 450 million worldwide (World Health Organization [WHO], 2003). According to the National Institute of Mental Health (NIMH), in the US, in 2012, an estimated 43.7 persons, aged 18 or older, were diagnosed with a mental illness in the past year. This represents approximately 18.6% of all American adults (as cited in NIMH, n.d.a). Beyond this, 9.6 million Americans are affected with SMI (as cited in NIMH, n.d.b). CalMEND, a program partnership of the California Department of Mental Health and the California Department of Health Care Services with funding provided via the Mental Health Services Act, has heightened awareness and focused additional research on the increased morbidity and mortality of persons with SMI (CalMEND, 2011).

In numerous articles and reviews dating back to 1989, the high mortality rate of people with SMI has been well documented. Recent literature reviews have estimated the mortality rates for persons with psychiatric diagnosis to range from two to three times as high as that of the general population (De Hert et al., 2011; Zolnierek, 2009). In fact, the risk for lost years of life has increased to 25 years earlier than that of the general population (Manderscheid, Druss, & Freemanm, 2008; Parks, Svedson, Singer, & Foti, 2006). These increased morbidity and mortality rates for this subgroup of our population are unacceptable (CalMEND, 2011). People with SMI and the “public healthcare systems that serve them face an urgent need to decrease the dramatic disparities in mortality and morbidity of those who have SMI” (CalMEND, 2011, p. 1).

Health of Persons with SMI

Many factors may contribute to the poor physical health of persons with SMI. The increased morbidity and mortality rates of persons with SMI has been found largely attributed to a higher prevalence of modifiable risk factors related to individual lifestyle choices (Parks et al., 2006). Another contributory factor is that co-occurring medical conditions go unidentified and/or untreated in persons with SMI and significantly shorten their life span (Gill, Murphy, Swarbrick, Spagnolo, & Zechner, 2009). As a result, individuals with SMI die at a much younger age and lose decades of potential life (Parks et al., 2006). The morbidity rate of persons with SMI is a serious public health crisis. Hence, the importance of detecting and treating medical conditions in those challenged with SMI is paramount.

Medical Care of Persons with SMI

Individuals with SMI experience disparities in healthcare (Cummings, Lucas, & Druss, 2013). The 2003 National Comorbidity Survey Replication (NCS-R) found that more than 68% of adults with a mental disorder had at least one chronic medical condition. Additionally, 29% of people with a medical disorder were found to have a comorbid mental health condition (Goodell, Druss, & Walker, 2011). This subgroup of the population has a higher rate of medical illness than the general population (Manderscheid et al., 2008).

A recent systematic review conducted by Mitchell, Malone, and Doebbeling (2009) found that across disease states, in general, the existence of mental illness seems to affect the quality of care. Strong evidence was found to support inequalities in medical care, which disadvantaged those with SMI (Mitchell et al., 2009). In some cases, the

difference in care approached 50% of the comparative standard, and rarely did persons with SMI receive higher quality care (Mitchell et al., 2009). Mitchell et al. (2009) found that persons with SMI attended appointments less often for preventive and routine care. Additionally, this care may be ineffective, and the quality of this care may be unsatisfactory in different medical settings. These gaps in routine care were found to be most notable in general medicine and cardiovascular care, and they may be present in diabetes care (Mitchell et al., 2009). In a 2013 study conducted by van Hasselt et al. (2013), persons with SMI had “insufficient contact” with their medical healthcare providers (p. 254). People with schizophrenia were also found to receive less treatment for their medical conditions than the general population (Vahia et al., 2008).

Persons with SMI have been found to have fewer routine preventive services, lower rates of cardiovascular procedures, and worse diabetes care (Druss, Rosenheck, Desai, & Perlin, 2002). Additionally, this subgroup is dying from “largely treatable conditions associated with modifiable risk factors such as smoking, obesity, substance abuse, and inadequate medical care” (Barry & Huskamp, 2011, p. 973). Screening, treatment, and management are core components of basic services for those with SMI (Parks & Pollack, 2005, p. 7). As the evidence suggests, the medical needs of those with SMI are not adequately addressed.

Barriers to Medical Care of Persons with SMI

Quite often, persons with SMI fail to receive sufficient preventive and diagnostic care or high quality medical treatment (Parks et al., 2006). One variable that impedes the diagnosis and treatment of medical conditions in this population is the lack of provider education on how to work collaboratively with people with SMI to assist them in

reducing their co-morbidities (Swarbrick, Hutchinson, & Gill, 2008). In a study examining adults with SMI, this population was found to have statistically significant decreased odds of having a primary care provider (PCP) and statistically significant increased odds of reporting difficulty accessing healthcare (Bradford et al., 2008). Other barriers to medical care for this population include a lack of financial resources, medical insurance, and recognition of symptoms by healthcare providers; transportation issues; the patient's lack of awareness of physical symptoms and an inability to describe medical problems; difficulties negotiating the healthcare system; and service fragmentation among the mental health and medical service delivery system (Gill et al., 2009; Muir-Cochrane, 2006).

Adherence

Over the past three decades, patient adherence has been of great concern in attempts to understand the limitations in the process of effective and efficient medical care delivery (DiMatteo, Lepper, & Croghan, 2000). In an extensive meta-analysis conducted by DiMatteo et al. in 2000, the relationship between depression and non-compliance was found substantial and significant with an odds ratio of 3.03 (95% confidence interval, 1.96–4.89). This indicates that depressed patients are three times more likely to fail to adhere to medical recommendations than nondepressed patients (Dimatteo et al., 2000).

Research has shown that lack of adherence spans a variety of settings and affects almost half of all medical patients in the US (Dimatteo et al., 2000). Patients were found to lack adherence to the physician's recommendations for both the prevention and treatment of acute and/or chronic conditions (Dimatteo et al., 2000). Nonadherence may

include failing to take medication correctly, failing to adhere to a prescribed diet or form of exercise, and failing to attend appointments, and/or continuing lifestyles that endanger the patient's health. Growing evidence suggests that patients' lack of adherence has a consistently negative effect on treatment goals and outcomes (DiMatteo et al., 2000).

In a national, cross-sectional study of over 310,000 patients, lack of adherence was also noted in persons with mental illness receiving care for diabetes (Frayne et al., 2005). Additionally, over 60% of persons with SMI reported having difficulty taking medications, attending medical appointments, and recognizing symptoms (Skinner et al., 1999). Frayne et al. postulated the benefits of integrated medical and mental health services to optimize the medical care of persons with SMI (Frayne et al., 2005).

Healthcare Integration

The importance of integrating medical and mental healthcare and to treat the person rather than the specific disease has been recognized for some time. As healthcare reforms and transformation has evolved, an increasing number of articles have been written on collaboration and integration of care, in particular, regarding the integration of traditional primary care and mental health care. Parks and Pollack (2005) noted that increased integration of behavioral health and physical healthcare services should be a priority at the national, state, local, and person levels. It is widely anticipated that the integration of primary care and behavioral health services will be a key part of healthcare transformation and reform in the near future (Collins, Heuson, Munger, & Wade, 2010). Forms of integration and effective care coordination have begun to show enhancements and improvements in quality of care, quality of life, and access to care.

Recently, in conjunction with the Mental Health Parity and Addictions Equity Act of 2008 (MHPAEA), and in line with the first phase of implementation of the Patient Protection and ACA of 2010, substantial effort and emphasis have been placed on integrating mental health care into primary care settings (Barry & Huskamp, 2011). As such, extensive evidence supports effective ways to detect and treat mental health and addiction in primary care settings (Barry & Huskamp, 2011). However, the physical healthcare needs of those with SMI are not often served in the traditional primary healthcare setting. The Lewin Group (2012) noted that persons with SMI experience benefits of increased access to care and improved care experiences as result of the integration of physical healthcare into behavioral health organizations. Integrated care has also been linked to improved health and decreased risk of adverse outcomes (Lewin Group, 2012, p. 3). These initiatives have also been shown to reduce costs over time (CalMEND, 2011).

In one systematic review of interventions designed to improve the general medical care for persons with mental disorders, the authors found the key element to collaborative care approaches is a functionally integrated care team (Druss & von Esenwein, 2005). Within the systematic review authored by Druss and von Esenwein (2005), three studies used team-based approaches based upon Wagner's CCM to utilize multidisciplinary teams that included both physical health and mental health providers. These three trials took place in large, integrated systems: two in the Veteran's Administration and one in a large Health Maintenance Organization in California (Druss & von Esenwein, 2005). To date, little evidence supports integrating physical healthcare

into a community mental health setting. Hence, this project aims to participate in creating the foundation for this evidence.

Models of Integrated Care

Various approaches can be used to integrate care. In 2013, SAMHSA-HRSA CIHS, in coordination with the National Council for Community Behavioral Healthcare (NCCBH), published “A Standard Framework for Levels of Integrated Healthcare” (Health, Wise, & Reynolds, 2013). The overarching framework has three main categories of care—coordinated care, co-located care, and integrated care—with two levels of degrees in each of the main categories. This framework has also been supported by the Milbank report titled, “Evolving Models of Behavioral Health Integration in Primary Care” (Collins et al., 2010). Hence, these categories and levels of care have been set as the national framework for care integration in the US and will be utilized in this project. However, limited evidence demonstrates the effectiveness of various interventions intended to enhance the physical health of persons with SMI (Tranter, Irvine, & Collins, 2012). Tranter et al. (2012) found that multimodal interventions and health promotion/education interventions were associated with positive outcomes for persons with SMI. In the limited number of existing studies that evaluate the levels of medical care and preventive screenings in integrated healthcare models, Collins et al. (2011) found that persons with SMI receiving integrated care have increased rates of diagnosis for chronic conditions, cervical cancer screenings, colon cancer screenings, and labs, eye exams, and cholesterol checks compared to the general Medicaid population.

In addition, in a randomized control study conducted by the Veteran’s Administration, which evaluated outcomes and behaviors of persons with SMI assigned

to receive medical care integrated in the mental health setting, the sample was found to be more likely to receive preventive treatment and visit a PCP, but less likely to visit the emergency department or report problems with coordination of care, and had significantly greater improvement in health overall, without increased total healthcare costs (Druss, Rohrbaugh, Levinson, & Rosenheck, 2001).

Co-location Model of Integration

Co-location approaches intend to integrate care and improve the physical healthcare of persons with SMI. Co-location models aim to incorporate primary healthcare capability into behavioral health organizations (Lewin Group, 2012). One way this could be done is by bringing PCPs on staff, either permanently or on a contract basis, to address the physical health needs of individuals treated by the behavioral health organization (Peek & the National Integration Academy Council, 2013). In this type of co-location model, behavioral and physical healthcare providers work together to address the comprehensive needs of the individuals at the behavioral health center. Additionally, general screening, such as blood pressure and body mass index (BMI), and wellness activities, such as smoking cessation classes or yoga classes, may be offered on-site and targeted specifically to individuals and families with behavioral health issues and concerns (Behavioral Health Integration Capacity Assessment, 2014).

These approaches can be conceptualized along a continuum that ranges from modest steps to integrate care to more grand efforts to create a single integrated system (Kaiser Commission on Medicaid and the Uninsured, 2014). One such type of integration is referred to as co-location of services (Collins et al., 2010; Heath, Wise, & Reynolds, 2013). Community health centers are said to be the “leaders in the ‘co-

location' of physical and behavioral healthcare at the same site" (Kaiser Commission on Medicaid and the Uninsured, 2014, p. 1).

The ACA authorized \$50 million in fiscal year 2010 and allocated additional funds in 2014 for the SAMHSA to provide grants to integrate services for persons with SMI and comorbid medical conditions within community-based behavioral health treatment settings (Barry & Huskamp, 2011). Studies on these specific co-location models that bring primary care into behavioral health community health settings are still in their beginning stages. However, this model has the potential to reduce lifestyle risk factors and improve the overall physical health of persons with SMI.

Barriers to Healthcare Integration

A variety of factors create barriers to effective healthcare provision for persons with SMI including resource separation of physical and mental healthcare facilities, a lack of clarity as to whom takes responsibility for the physical healthcare of persons with SMI, a lack of integration between medicine and psychiatry, and a lack of continuity of care (Druss, 2007; Lawrence & Kisely, 2010). In a study published in 2008, CMHCs that were trying to integrate and/or coordinate mental and physical health services identified barriers such as reimbursement, work force limitations, physical plant constraints, and a lack of options for referrals to community medical providers (Druss et al., 2008).

Currently, there is insufficient evidence from high quality studies to determine the effectiveness or the appropriate level of integrated care (Butler et al., 2008). Beyond this, very limited evidence is available for integrating primary care into specialty mental health settings (Butler et al., 2008). Yet, the model of embedding primary care services

in a CMHC has been considered, theoretically, to be the most effective strategy for persons with SMI (Bazelton Center for Mental Health Law, 2004; Parks et al., 2006).

Currently, limited data specifically addresses effective methods to improve the general physical health of persons receiving treatment in a CMHC. A study by Scharf et al. (2013) reviewed the characteristics and early implementation experiences of community behavioral health centers that, as a result of grant funding from SAMHSA, integrated primary care into programs for persons with SMI. Scharf et al. (2013) found that, initially, less than half of the behavioral health agencies offered any primary care services prior to receiving grant funding. In the early stages of integrating the services, these agencies noted barriers caused by difficulty recruiting and retaining qualified staff; issues related to data collection, use of the electronic records, licensing and approvals; and physical space constraints. In the later stages of implementation, problems with staffing and data collection remained and the new challenge of patient recruitment emerged (Scharf et al., 2013).

METHODS

The method for this project was a case study of the grant implementation, including an evaluation of outcomes. The decision to report this analysis as a case study was formulated to allow all aspects of implementation to be reported, discussed, and analyzed, including process outcomes. Generalized program evaluations, which are intended to examine a process or outcomes of an organization, are conducted to attain greater understanding of the program and to improve practice. Program evaluations require systematic collection and analysis of information in order to make decisions about program implementation and improve program effectiveness (Holly, 2014). A case study provides the most global and all-encompassing opportunity for analysis and evaluation of multidimensional processes, interactions, and relationships, thus allowing a deeper understanding of a complex process and providing a detailed contextual analysis of events and their relationships (Holly, 2014).

The case study was constructed by examining the development and contents of the two grants and the implementation efforts that followed the awarding of the grants. Since the intent of the agencies is to continue to pursue the provision of integrated care, the case study also served as a formative evaluation of both concrete data points and process outcomes. Formative evaluations differ from other types of evaluations in that they are ongoing and enable the evaluator(s) to make informed judgments regarding the status and ability to achieve the intended goals of the program (Holly, 2014, p. 160). Formative program evaluations are structured to provide information and findings that are timely, concrete, and used for immediate and ongoing program development and improvement. They aim to assist in developing and improving programs from an early

stage (Holly, 2014, p 157). It is often in the early stages that opportunities for influence are likely to be most significant (Dehar, Casswell, & Duignan, 1993).

As per Holly (2014), the use of formative evaluation, while standard in other arenas, is a fairly new concept in healthcare and may not be well-suited for evaluating all types of healthcare programs. Greater application of formative evaluation to healthcare programs in the future holds the potential to create more effective and well-designed programs and increase the understanding of the factors that influence program outcomes (Dehar et al., 1993).

Grant Analysis

The data that supported the applications for the grants was uncovered and the expected deliverables outlined. Recorded data relating to the services provided and the outcomes of those services were analyzed and evaluated. Discussions with the principal facility staff involved in the implementation revealed the decision-making processes and various decisions that shaped the implementation, including the barriers encountered and how these barriers shaped the eventual outcomes. The actual deliverables were compared with the expected deliverables.

This case study evaluated specifically the agency's efforts, the progress made, the barriers encountered, and the resulting culture shift that occurred during the implementation of two grants aimed at increasing the level of integrated care provided at the CMHC. Additionally, this project evaluated the efforts to navigate complex healthcare systems and coordinate mental and physical healthcare delivery. The case study provided explanations, examinations, and discussions of the specific grant deliverables.

Beyond the data specified by the grant, additional data and information were gathered from the initiatives and discussions of the CMHC staff. An analysis of the data and information obtained during the grant was performed in Excel, using pivot table functions and cross-tabulations. The data points included in the case study are discussed in the results section, while the case study and a description of the integration process are found in Appendix A.

Ethical Considerations

Of utmost importance is ensuring the protection of human subjects in all research settings. This project evaluation involved, in part, a review of de-identified data generated by the grant initiatives at the CMHC and, therefore, did not meet criteria for a full Institutional Review Board (IRB) review. Permission was obtained from the CMHC to conduct the program evaluation (see Appendix B). A waiver was granted by IRB at California State University Los Angeles (see Appendix C).

RESULTS

While some of the expected grant outcomes were met, others were not. As a result of the *Integrated Healthcare Project* grant, the mental health center retained a licensed vocational nurse (LVN), instead of a medical assistant, and a primary care doctor, instead of a nurse practitioner, who were co-located at the CMHC two mornings per week to provide medical care. The CMHC's members obtained care from these primary care specialists as needed. A total of 159 unduplicated members were seen by the PCPs, which exceeded the expected grant outcome of 125 members to be treated by the on-site PCPs.

However, the second measurable grant outcome to connect or re-connect 100 eligible individuals with a community public insurance/managed Medi-Cal provider, to ensure ongoing access to care, proved more challenging and was not met. Throughout the grant period, 59 persons who were seen were uninsured. Of the 98 persons covered by health insurance, 62 people were aware of their insured status and 36 people were unaware that they were covered under a health insurance plan. As shown in Table 1, by the end of the grant, 34 of the 59 initially uninsured members had been connected with insurance, 9 members had applied for insurance and were awaiting responses, and 16 members remained uninsured and unconnected with an insurer. While 73% of the previously uninsured members seen under the grant had either applied for insurance or become insured, this did not meet the 100-member criterion set forth by the grant, as only 59 uninsured members were treated.

Table 1

Insured Status of Members

BASELINE	POST				Total
	Insured & Aware	Insured & Unaware	Applied	No Insurance	
Insured & Aware	62				62
Insured & Unaware	36				36
Applied	2				2
No Insurance	34		9	16	59
Total	134		9	16	159

Additionally, the third grant outcome (collaborating with community PCPs to integrate physical and mental health treatment and medication issues for 125 individuals with multiple needs) was not met. The outcome of being “connected” to a community PCP was operationalized as having seen the community PCP for 2 or more visits during the grant reporting period.

One hundred fifty-nine members received services funded by the grant. Of these, 98 members entered treatment with the on-site PCP without a connection with a community PCP. As shown in Table 2, by the end of the grant, of the 98 members who entered without a connection to a community PCP, 29 became connected with a community PCP, 22 had had a first visit with a community PCP, 25 had identified a community PCP for their care, and 22 remained unconnected to a community PCP. As previously mentioned, the grant criterion related to this was to connect 125 persons with a community PCP. This goal was impossible to meet because only 98 persons who came to the CMHC were unconnected to a community PCP.

Table 2

Member's PCP Status

BASELINE	POST					Total
	Connected	First Visit	Identified	Not Connected	Unknown	
Connected	15					15
First Visit	2					2
Identified	24	5	14			43
Not Connected	29	22	25	27		98
Unknown	1					1
Total	71	27	39	22	0	159

Hence, in the end, 122 members (77%) identified, had an initial visit, or became connected with a community PCP, 22 (14%) remained without connection to a community PCP, and 15 (9%) maintained their pre-existing connection with their community PCP. Since members were seen until the end of the reporting period, it is possible that some were awaiting a first or second appointment with a community PCP; this was not tracked. Additionally, it is possible that some members were not required to see their community PCP a second time during the specified grant reporting period because a second appointment was not deemed necessary.

The second grant, *Access to Physical Health Care for People with Serious Mental Illness*, also aimed to increase the level of integrated care at the CMHC and had multiple deliverables. See Appendix A for the case study description of grant processes and the barriers encountered in implementation. Ultimately, the electronic Health Risk and Response Registry (HRRR) that was envisioned was not created due to the various challenges and barriers presented while trying to fully utilize and reconfigure the existing EHR. Hence, instead of creating the HRRR in the existing EHR, a paper version was created. The companion document, “My Medical Visit” form, was created but not

implemented. The new Community Health Resource Guide was created but has not yet been made available to staff; thus, no staff training on new materials has occurred.

Please see Appendix A for further discussion and explanation of the grant deliverables.

Barriers and amendments to the grant process are discussed in both the discussion section and the case study.

DISCUSSION

Implementation

The implementation of this project was fraught with a number of barriers and challenges. Some of the grant deliverables for the *Integrated Healthcare Project* grant were met, while others were not. The grant deliverables for the *Access to Physical Health Care for People with Serious Mental Illness* grant were not completed in their entirety. A full discussion of the implementation efforts and outcomes for this project are detailed in Appendix A.

Evaluation

In order to adequately evaluate the changes, or lack thereof, in the agency, it is important to note where the agency started. The philosophical foundation of this particular CMHC is that of psychosocial rehabilitation and recovery. As such, this model differs from others in that it does not espouse or coincide with the medical model. This, in part, created the concerns, reluctance, and lack of enthusiasm of the leadership of this agency, as the integrated care models appear to utilize a more traditional medical model. Despite hesitation from some leadership at the CMHC, there was also support of a bi-directional nature, originating at the top level of senior management of the parent mental health agency, who were the instigators of the grant opportunities. Support was also evident in the Director of Healthcare Management, the psychiatric nurse practitioners, some of the nurses, the PCP, the PC nurse, and some of the service line staff. Various levels of support were observed ranging from idealistic support of the vision to an eagerness to jump in and consider programmatic changes to support the provision of a higher level of integrated care.

As a result of the grant initiatives, the agency has changed. Of the current members served, 159 members who had not previously received primary care services have now received these important medical services. While neither staff referrals nor self-referrals increased over the life of the one-year grant, more staff became aware of the on-site PC care services, and the number of members being served continues to remain steady. Discussions about the provision of integrated care services and methods to achieve a higher level of integrated care have increased. Additionally, discussions have been held on sustainability, program reconfiguration to support sustainability, and partnering with more PCPs in the local community. The HRRR changed from existing in the EHR to being created in paper form. This form is currently being used by three teams to gather information about the members served by those teams. The My Medical Visit form was completed; however, it is not yet being utilized. In addition, while the Community Health Resource Guide is not yet in use, plans have been made to make it available to all staff and keep it maintained with updated information.

Most notably, the parent mental health company has strengthened its commitment to providing a higher level of integrated care, and the CMHC is now an active member in discussions with the mental health parent company regarding applying for a SAMHSA grant funding to provide integrated care. The CMHC is actively working with the parent company to conceptualize and design an infrastructure to promote and provide integrated care. While there is still a lack of internal coordination at the CMHC, the most staunch resisters in leadership have softened their stance and have started participating in discussions about the need for and importance of providing integrated care to its members. Both the parent company and the CMHC are in agreement that the support of

leadership for integrated care efforts is an integral and fundamental component to the success of providing integrated care. There is also greater recognition of the realistic barriers and feasibility issues in providing integrated care as well as partnering with community PCPs. There is a renewed commitment and understanding of the importance of having co-located (on-site) primary care services, which include nurse care coordinators/nurse navigators.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Given the complexities of providing integrated care, it is not surprising that challenges and barriers were encountered by these initiatives. Implementing a new or revised model of care provision into an existing system and/or conducting an organizational culture shift are iterative processes. These processes can be enhanced or diminished by such factors as leadership, organizational commitment, implementation strategy, and organizational flexibility and adaptation. One significant challenge for the first grant initiative was created by the lack of proactive planning for the grant's implementation. This challenge stemmed from the CMHC's lack of awareness of the grant application. The fact that the grant application and proposed implementation plan had been constructed by the parent mental health company without input from or coordination with the CMHC created a host of challenges that affected operational efficiencies, implementation timelines, and staff commitment. During the preliminary discussions of the grant and when the resistance of the CMHC leadership became clear, the parent mental health company took the opportunity to share its vision with the CMHC leadership. Clarification was provided that these grant initiatives were viewed as opportunities for the CMHC to "practice," seek learning lessons and begin initiating change within the agency to prepare for future integrated care efforts. However, despite the clarification provided, the CMHC leadership was not fully supportive of the grant and, consequently, maintained a skeptical and distant connection with the grant implementation and process. This impeded some efforts of others to implement new processes to achieve the grant deliverables.

In another example, the grant provisions called for the hiring of a primary care nurse practitioner and medical assistant. However, because of a change in commitment

by the planned partner, a new partner was solicited and a primary care physician and a LVN were selected to provide the on-site primary care services. These changes proved to have exceptionally positive outcomes based on the enthusiasm, flexibility, demeanor, and commitment of the staff selected. These intangible qualities are difficult to ascertain proactively and may serve as critical factors for similar situations. Hence, when selecting staff to provide team-based integrated care, factors other than a candidate's educational pedigree and work experience should be considered. Personal factors and the ability to connect and engage staff and members are fundamental and imperative qualities for working effectively with this population in this type of setting.

Another challenge to the implementation of the initiatives was the resource constrained environment of the non-profit CMHC. The resources in limited supply were the availability and the ability of staff to prioritize their time to devote effort and energy to the grant deliverables. A joint challenge to this was creating flexibility in the organization to adapt staff roles to incorporate the new facets of the grant requirements. These intended alterations to organizational process were resisted both subtly and overtly. While these challenges are not novel to this particular CMHC, they were significantly compounded by the lack of leadership support and thereby further diminished the priorities of the grant deliverables, as well as the ability to effectively implement the grants and achieve the desired outcomes.

Chronic Care Model Constructs

As intended in this doctoral project and through the grant initiatives, several of the constructs in the CCM (CalMEND, 2011) were affected by the grant initiatives: decision support, clinical information systems, self-management support, and delivery system

design. The grant deliverables did drive the agency toward effecting change in these areas; however, most of the intended changes have yet to be realized. For example, once implemented and usable, both the Community Health Resource Guide and the My Medical Visit form are expected to effect change in the level of self-management support provided to members, thereby enhancing members' abilities to more ably self-manage aspects of their health. More broadly, and not a recognized goal of this project, these changes are also positioned to effect change in the higher level Chronic Care construct of the community (Resources and Policies) (CalMEND, 2011).

The Chronic Care delivery system design construct lies at the heart of the grant implementation efforts. As a result of the challenges and barriers encountered in the grant initiatives, organizational and infrastructure changes to support the provision of a higher level of integrated care are under discussion and consideration. While the current delivery system design is sufficient for care provision, the intent to add primary care and care navigation to the repertoire of services the CMHC provides necessitates not only a shift in the culture of the CMHC but also in the design and functionality of the team-based care.

The most notable area of change in the CCM constructs (CalMEND, 2011) is in the area of decision support. The grant initiative and implementation that embedded on-site primary care in the CMHC is having a profound effect on the culture and the provision of integrated care in the CMHC. Hence, the maintenance and growth of this service is critical. Recognition of the importance of this service is growing, particularly among the leadership of the parent mental health company and the CMHC staff. Perhaps

through the combination of efforts by the grassroots staff and the leadership of the parent mental health company, further change will occur.

The construct of clinical information system proved to be the most challenging. This construct specifically relates to the organization of patient and population data and incorporates performance monitoring and quality improvements efforts. The EHR at the CMHC, though in use for 18 months, had not been utilized to its fullest potential. The lack of full use and the rampant use of “work-around” methods became clear during the implementation efforts of the grant initiatives. Additionally, the lack of both clinical performance measures and an effective quality improvement process was highlighted. As such, both the CMHC and the parent mental health company are considering methods to implement and strengthen these areas.

As a result of the initiatives’ structures and deliverables, change was intended to be implemented in several areas. The difficulty in achieving these deliverables was compounded by the fact that these initiatives were thrust upon the CMHC without prior planning. One might argue that it may be more efficacious to streamline efforts and target change in one or two areas at a time. Others might argue that change is best implemented by destabilizing the system, which requires change in numerous areas simultaneously. This is an area that requires strategic decision making based upon the understanding of one’s own organization as well as knowledge of leadership strategies and organizational change theory. One theory relevant to this evaluation is the Diffusion of Innovations theory by Everett Rogers (1962).

Akin to Prochaska’s Stages of Change model (Prochaska & DiClemente, 1982), the Roger’s Diffusion of Innovation theory postulates stages of the innovation-decision

process (Rogers, 1962). In recognizing the varied levels of change readiness within the CMHC and the parent mental health company, one can also note the parallel stages in Roger's model. Specifically, the varying levels of awareness, interest, support, and commitment of the CMHC staff for integrated care represent the stages of change in Prochaska's model of precontemplation, contemplation, preparation, and action (Prochaska & DiClemente, 1982). These stages correlate with the knowledge stage, persuasion stage, decision stage, and implementation stage in Roger's model (1962). The grant initiatives call for action and implementation, which theoretically and logistically were not fully possible given that the leadership of the CMHC was not invested in the grant implementation.

According to Roger's Diffusion of Innovations theory (1962), the innovation process in organizations is much more complex than the same process by an individual. Rogers (1962) stated that the innovation process for an organization has two broad activities, initiation and implementation, which comprise five subset stages: agenda-setting, matching, redefining/restructuring, clarifying, and routinizing. Once again, the challenge underlying the grant initiatives was that the majority of staff at the CMHC and the parent mental health company were not in one or two congruent categories but, instead, ranged from the earliest stage of agenda setting to the early stages of implementation, which include redefining/restructuring and clarifying.

Rogers (1962) also purported the concept of adopter categorization, which notes the existence of innovators, early adopters, early majority, late majority, and laggards. Given that the notion of providing integrated care came into discussion in the early 1970s, this is not viewed as an innovative concept. It is, however, a very timely and

pertinent topic that is currently and actively being investigated and funded in efforts to find effective and sustainable models. Hence, while there may be some innovative individuals attempting to construct new models of care, it is appropriate to view the CMHC's and parent mental health company's efforts to provide integrated care in the early majority to later majority category. In this light, it is advisable to evaluate the CMHC's current status and progress towards providing fully integrated care within the context of the SAMHSA Six Levels of Collaborative/Integration tables (Heath et al., 2013). These tables delineate the expected processes in different levels of care ranging from the least integrated form of care, coordinated care, to fully integrated care. These tables also highlight the key differentiators in patient experience, clinical delivery, and business models, as well as advantages and weaknesses between the six stages of care ranging from coordinated care to integrated care. Prior to the grant initiatives, this project evaluated the CMHC at Level 1. Please see Table 3 in Appendix D. However, following the grant initiatives and the organizational and culture changes that occurred while attempting to implement these initiatives, the CMHC has moved to a Level 2/Level 3. The CMHC now provides on-site primary care services, attempts to share some information between the mental health and physical health providers, and has reduced the barriers to receiving care. Continued efforts are recommended for the CMHC to continue to progress along the continuum towards providing fully integrated care.

Recommendations

Without doubt, the provision of integrated care is not a simple process. As has been made clear in this project evaluation and case study, augmenting and reconfiguring an existing system to provide integrated care is a challenging and complex transition.

Broadly speaking, agencies need to find sources to fund primary care services, train staff, strengthen their connections with community PCPs, track relevant data, and disseminate findings. To do this, some key points can be related to not only the CMHC in this project but also other CMHCs interested in increasing the level of integrated care they provide. For such agencies, there must be a vision accompanied by an organized, thoughtful, and sensible plan to pursue that vision (Northouse, 2013). The intent and support of leadership and management must be aligned in this vision (Grossman & Valgia, 2013; Northouse, 2013). Grant applications and deliverables promised must be decided in conjunction with the team of people directly responsible for deliverables and implementations. Planning for implementation(s) must be conducted amongst relevant staff. Internal discussions to share information and vet concerns must occur prior to deciding upon and securing external partners. Open channels of communication must be established and maintained to identify successes, barriers, and areas of concern (Northouse, 2013). EHR challenges are real, can be pervasive, and may often be underestimated. Whether these challenges prove insurmountable is yet to be seen. Decisions about data collection must be made proactively and viewed with the desired results in mind. EHR capabilities as well as staff skill sets and abilities must be considered prior to beginning data tracking projects. The costs of initial investment and ongoing maintenance of an EHR must be considered and projected. While these functions may seem daunting, the pursuit of providing integrated care is a worthy and necessary goal. The potential for increasing the already shortened life spans of those with SMI warrants the community's best efforts in creating sustainable integrated care models and providing quality and cost-effective care through these models.

Recommendations for Program Implementation

Several suggestions will support the CMHC and the parent mental health agency along their journey to providing more fully integrated care to their members. The recommendations for CMHC and the parent mental health company are as follows:

- restructure the existing treatment teams to include a nurse navigator position, which would not only change the culture of the team but also create room for growth;
- secure additional and sustainable funding/grants to continue the current embedded primary care services, allow the continuation of services, and begin to incorporate appropriate specialty services, i.e., podiatry, dental, and vision;
- address challenges created by the existing EHR, including the lack of a query function and the lack of EHR integration of psychiatric and medical data.

Evaluation Recommendations

In order to evaluate the progress of current and future efforts to increase the level of integrated care provided, various data points and benchmarks should be assessed at routine timeframes and compared to previous data. Such evaluative questions include the following:

- Has the CMHC secured additional/sustainable funding to further its efforts in providing integrated care to its members?
- How many persons have received primary care services on-site at the CMHC in the past year compared to the previous year? Have more members been referred to care by their case manager or are there more self-referrals?

- How many persons have become connected with a PCP in the community compared to the previous year? Are the first 159 members still connected with their PCP?
- How many members have been connected with health insurance compared to the previous year?
- Are the members getting better? Evaluate BMI, smoking cessation, and substance use.
- What is the current culture and organizational structure of the CMHC's staff and leadership?
- Have staff received training on the importance of the CMHC's provision of integrated care?

In healthcare today, we need to move towards providing more integrated care for all people. Figuring out what the challenges and barriers are, and how to successfully navigate them is imperative so that we can provide quality and cost efficient care to all members of our population, including those with serious mental illness.

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APPENDIX A

A TALE OF TWO GRANTS—A CASE STUDY OF ORGANIZATIONAL CHANGE

A case study is one way of reporting an evaluation as an illustrative example of a single case. This case study focused on the efforts of a community mental health center (CMHC) and its parent mental health company to implement changes to provide a higher level of integrated care to the people it serves. This case study provides a report of the outcomes, an evaluation of the process and progress, and recommendations.

Initial Status of Integrated Care

This descriptive case study highlights a nationally recognized CMHC in Southern California that is dedicated to promoting mental health recovery and wellness to persons with serious mental illness (SMI). This CMHC aims to blend all the parts of mental health recovery—treatment, rehabilitation, family and community support, and self-help—to help adults with SMI achieve self-sufficiency and independency, and integrate into the community. Primary facets of this program include an emphasis on choice, equality between staff and the people served, encouragement of continued growth, and an environment of strong support. With a focus on quality of life goals and outcomes, this CMHC helps people to live and work, and become involved in the community, while measuring these outcomes to ensure effectiveness and accountability. This CMHC program tailors services to each individual's psychiatric, employment, housing, substance abuse recovery, financial, and educational needs. Physical health care was not a component of the repertoire of services offered by this CMHC.

This story begins back in 2007 when the then Chief Executive Officer (CEO) of the mental health agency, parent company of the CMHC, expressed his interest in

becoming a Federally Qualified Health Center (FQHC). The then CEO brought the CMHC Medical Director to a national meeting to learn about the process of becoming a FQHC. Dismayed by the multi-layered complexities and seeming barriers, the FQHC status was not pursued. The then CEO and Chief Operating Officer (COO) began investigating Accountable Care Organization (ACO) partnerships in their local area. Partnerships were established with local agencies providing primary care services to adults and children.

Nationwide, many state agencies, health plans, and provider systems have begun implementing medical and behavioral health integration strategies to bridge the gaps in primary healthcare and behavioral healthcare (Kaiser Commission on Medicaid and the Uninsured, 2014). Some form of integration is seen as the best path to enhance and improve quality of care, quality of life, access to care, and to reduce costs (CalMEND, 2011). Yet, very little evidence is currently available regarding effective medical and behavioral health integration strategies for persons with SMI (Barry & Huskamp, 2011).

These approaches to integration can be conceptualized along a continuum that ranges from modest steps to integrate care to more grand efforts to create a single integrated system (Kaiser Commission on Medicaid and the Uninsured, 2014). One such type of integration is referred to as the co-location of services (Collins, Heuson, Munger, & Wade, 2010; Heath, Wise, & Reynolds, 2013). Community health centers are said to be the “leaders in the ‘co-location’ of physical and behavioral health care at the same site” (Kaiser Commission on Medicaid and the Uninsured, 2014, p. 1).

Co-location models of integration intend to integrate care and improve the physical healthcare of persons with SMI. Some co-location models aim to incorporate

primary healthcare capability into behavioral health organizations (Lewin Group, 2012). One way of achieving this is by bringing primary care providers (PCPs) on staff, either permanently or on a contract basis, to address the physical health needs of individuals being treated by the behavioral health organization (Peek & the National Integration Academy Council, 2013). In this type of co-location model, behavioral and physical healthcare providers work together to address the comprehensive needs of the individuals at the behavioral health center. Studies on these specific co-location models that bring primary care into a behavioral health community health setting are still in their beginning stages. Yet, this co-location model has the potential to reduce lifestyle risk factors and improve the overall physical health of persons with SMI.

During this time, the Affordable Care Act (ACA) authorized \$50 million in fiscal year 2010 and allocated additional funds in 2014 for the Substance Abuse and Mental Health Services Administration (SAMHSA) to provide grants to integrate services for persons with mental illness and comorbid medical conditions within community-based behavioral health treatment settings (Barry & Huskamp, 2011). Even though the parent mental health company applied for the SAMHSA grant funds with the aid and ideology of the CMHC's Medical Director, it was not an awarded recipient. However, the interest of the parent mental health agency to promote integrated care services was solidified.

Owing to the strong commitment of the senior management of the CMHC's parent agency, continued efforts were made to investigate alternative grant opportunities to secure the funding needed to provide integrated mental and physical healthcare. Financial support and integration are thought to have been the main drivers for these efforts.

During this time, the CMHC Medical Director attended a National Alliance on Mental Illness (NAMI) lecture, which highlighted the early deaths of persons with SMI compared to those without SMI. Additionally, it was noted that the Framingham Risk factors accounted for 92% of early deaths of the SMI population. This information prompted the CMHC Medical Director to examine the recent deaths and discharges of the CMHC, whereon he found that deaths of members in their late fifties to early sixties were seven times that of the national average. The timing of realizing this information coincided with new research information that attributed many illnesses in persons with SMI, such as metabolic syndrome, with the use of specific atypical antipsychotic medications. The convergence of these factors increased the CMHC Medical Director's concern about the physical healthcare and status of the persons being served by the mental health agency and the CMHC. This information, in conjunction with the growing national awareness of the disparate medical care for those with SMI and the fact that life spans of those with SMI are significantly shortened by the presence and lack of management of modifiable risk factors, prompted the mental health agency to commit to becoming a practice that addressed not only mental healthcare but also the physical healthcare needs of its members.

In 2009, the CMHC's nursing administrator assessed 500 individuals participating in the CMHC program. She identified that 26.5% had hypertension, 15.5% met the definition of obesity, 12.6% had diabetes mellitus, and 11.1% had cardiovascular disease. Additionally, 60% of members were uninsured and had limited access to primary care. In 2010, as a result of a county funded grant project, the mental health agency embarked upon its first integrated care innovations project with its local community partner, an

FQHC. This innovation project aimed to provide mental health and primary care services with a “street medicine” approach to homeless persons being served by the mental health agency. This integrated care project was the first foray for the mental health agency and its local community FQHC partner into primary care services. Further grant funding continued to be sought.

The Grants

Integrated Healthcare Project Grant

The parent mental health agency secured the first grant opportunity, titled *Integrated Healthcare Project*, from the California Community Foundation. The Chief Development and Communications Officer applied for the grant under the direction of the Chief Operating Officer at the parent agency of the CMHC. The one-year grant award (July 2013–June 2014) was intended to cover the expenses of embedding a nurse practitioner with medical assistant support into the CMHC two mornings per week to provide primary care services, including physical assessments and short-term treatment. The grant also covered the provision of a medical assistant to conduct screening, educate patients about conditions, and coordinate care by helping individuals apply for public insurance for ongoing care. The aims of the project were to provide primary screening and care, and health maintenance and education, and to pilot initial steps to develop a behavioral healthcare home for people with SMI. The agency planned to enhance its partnership with a local community partner, who was established as an FQHC and had served as a partner on a previous innovation project integrating primary care and mental health services using a “street medicine” approach for homeless people with mental illness. The grant was intended for use in the homeless assistance program in the CMHC,

which serves approximately 500 people. The requested and awarded grant amount of \$98,182 was dispersed in two intervals, first upon the awarding of the grant and second at the midpoint of the grant period. The grant was budgeted to cover expenses of a 0.15 FTE nurse practitioner salary, a medical assistant's full-time salary, medical supplies, cell phone, and mileage. The measurable objectives of the grant are as follows:

- conduct physical assessments and provide short-term primary care (average of 2–4 visits) and education to 125 individuals with SMI by embedding a part-time nurse practitioner at the CMHC,
- connect or re-connect 100 eligible individuals to a public insurance/managed Medi-Cal provider to ensure ongoing access to care, and
- collaborate with the physical healthcare provider to integrate physical and mental health treatment and medication issues for 125 individuals with multiple needs.

Integrated Healthcare Project Grant Implementation

The CMHC facility, where the grant was to be implemented, was unaware of the grant application until its award was announced. In fact, the grant was announced several days after the grant period had begun. The CMHC's staff had mixed reactions to integrated care efforts and receipt of the grant ranging from disinterest to skeptical cynicism and to tempered enthusiasm.

The CMHC staff discussed the grant award in provider, quality management, and leadership meetings. One immediate barrier encountered was the news that the existing FQHC primary care services partner was unable to participate in this project as had been expected and proposed in the grant. This led to concern and hesitation among some of

the staff at the CMHC. Some staff discussed the possibility of declining the grant, as it seemed too difficult to implement in such a short amount of time, especially without participation of the expected partner. The concern about grant acceptance was exacerbated by the absence of a Director of Nursing (DON) for approximately eighteen months. To further complicate the situation, a new Director of Healthcare Management, a revised position to include the DON's responsibilities, had just been hired, and the staff had to adjust to new administration along with new grant expectations. The agency staff comprises case managers, social workers, nurses, psychiatric nurse practitioners, psychiatrists, and administrative staff. Approximately seven nurses, who span four treatment teams, have a dual reporting structure, as they are supervised by both the Team Director and the Director of Healthcare Management.

Fortunately, the person hired to fill the role of Director of Healthcare Management was a registered nurse and public health nurse, who had previously worked at the CMHC as a case manager. The CMHC gladly welcomed her back into this new role. Her start date had been a few weeks prior to the announcement of the grant. Given the background of the Director of HealthCare Management and her background as a registered nurse and public health nurse, she understood and supported the vision of the grant and was assigned the role to oversee the grant implementation at the CMHC. She worked closely with the COO of the mental health parent agency to secure a new partner.

Through a pre-existing relationship with the local health department, the process outcomes were amended to identify a public health physician, instead of the intended nurse practitioner, to provide the primary care at the CMHC. Hence, a new partnership with the local public health agency was established. Additionally, a LVN was hired

instead of a medical assistant. As such, the implementation team at CMHC was solidified to include the public health physician, the LVN, the Director of Healthcare Management, and a psychiatric mental health nurse practitioner (PMHNP), who was also a Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) student. This core group of four were not only interested in implementing the grant but were also passionate about implementing their vision—shared with the parent mental health agency—to bring integrated care services to the members served by the CMHC. The Director of Healthcare Management and the PMHNP/DNP student had integral roles in navigating the barriers and challenges associated with the grant initiatives. In fact, since integrated care became the focus of the PMHNP's DNP project, she became the resource person and de facto leader for this project. The grant was delayed until November 2013 to secure a new partner for primary care services.

The original plan was for the PCP to utilize the exam room in the homeless assistance program. However, it was decided the PCP would require a larger room with a computer to conduct exams. This larger room, which was located in a different area of the CMHC in the general milieu, adjacent to several other programs, was dedicated to the PCP on the mornings he was on-site. The LVN was located a short distance from the PCP's exam room.

Based upon the grant's aim to assist those persons with SMI at risk of homelessness, the Director of Healthcare Management decided that the grant services, including PCP services, would be made available not only to those in the homeless assistance program (approximately 500 members) but also to those in all programs associated with the CMHC (approximately 1,330 members). Informational meetings

were held with all CMHC program leaders to explain the new on-site primary care services and to discuss how to refer members to these services. Informational flyers were posted for all CMHC program members about the new on-site primary care services encouraging use of these services through either a referral from a member's case manager or a member's self-referral.

One of the early internal barriers encountered was the resistance and hesitation to allow the PCP access to view and document in the electronic health record (EHR). After significant discussion with the Quality Assurance department of the parent mental health company, who had significant concerns about this option, a compromise was reached; the PCP would type his clinical notes for the LVN to enter into the member's EHR. Additionally, as a follow up to any member appointment, the LVN would email the member's visit summary to the case manager.

The implementation and execution of the grant prompted various discussions among the staff. Some of the notable questions concerned sustainability: When the grant funding is gone, will the CMHC continue to have an on-site PCP or LVN? How will this be funded? Are additional grants being sought to continue PCP/integrated care efforts? How do we continue to increase our efforts toward integrated care for members at the CMHC? Should this be a goal of the CMHC? Other areas of concern were the lack of standards of care policies within the CMHC, the lack of physical health monitoring within the agency separate from the PCP and LVN services, the varying levels of staff interest in addressing the physical healthcare of the members served, and the associated liabilities and risks. Leadership involvement and support was another area discussed. Key leaders of the CMHC were found to have opposing stances on the

importance of integration and methods to use to address the physical health of the CMHC members. It was unclear who the key stakeholders were within the agency. The addition of a new Chief Program Officer whose role was to oversee all programs of the mental health agency, including the CMHC, further confused the staff's understanding of the program leadership's philosophy towards integrated care.

Data Collection and Program Evaluation

Two months prior to the end of the grant, the PCP, LVN, PMHNP/DNP student, and Director of Healthcare Management finalized what data would be gathered from the members seen by the PCP and/or LVN during the grant period and how this data would be stored. The PCP expressed his interest in possibly preparing a journal article or presentation of the data as well as the experiences and learning from this project. A plan for data collection was established, which involved chart reviews of all members—a time-intensive task, which did not contribute to a strong program evaluation component. Discussions held at the outset of the grant, which suggested conducting a program evaluation of the grant processes, related changes, and data analysis, concluded that a summative evaluation was appropriate. However, news of the refunding the PCP and LVN for a longer period, through a different grant, prompted the switch from a summative evaluation to a formative evaluation. Additionally, the CEO of the CMHC's parent company informed the CMHC Medical Director that these grants were sought as a means of “practice” for the CMHC to begin its efforts in providing integrated care to its members, which further supported a formative evaluation.

Access to Physical Health Care for People with Serious Mental Illness Grant

In November 2013, the same month the *Integrated Healthcare Project* grant began, the Director of Healthcare Management was approached by the Chief Development Officer regarding the need for new and additional grant funding to further integrate the care efforts. After a brief phone call and general conversation about integrated care efforts at the CMHC, the grant application was submitted. The details of the grant application were not discussed with the CMHC staff and they were not involved in the development of the grant proposal. Once again, the CMHC facility, where the grant was to be executed, was largely unaware of the grant application except for the Director of Healthcare Management. This second grant opportunity was secured to allow the CMHC to move toward the provision of more integrated care by addressing the physical health needs of its members. The Chief Development and Communications Officer applied for this grant under the direction of the Chief Operating Officer at the CMHC's parent agency.

The grant, titled *ACA and Access to Physical Health Care for People with Serious Mental Illness* was awarded by the Robert Ellis Simon Foundation, was proposed to adjunctively build upon the efforts funded by the California Community Foundation grant. The grant specified the concerns of the mental health agency related to the ACA. As the ACA was set up to allow the large number of low-income individuals access to healthcare, the mental health agency postulated that persons with SMI will struggle to receive services due to the existing disparities in healthcare access. The mental health agency viewed 2014 as a transitional year to allow its main service program, the CMHC, to address the issue of persons with SMI receiving physical healthcare services. In

support of the larger county efforts to strengthen integration of mental and physical healthcare, the mental health agency sought to share its planning and piloting activities in this grant with fellow organizations. The following project goals proposed for improvement were as follows:

- CMHC system-wide assessment and access to primary healthcare treatment for adults with SMI, many of whom also have serious needs but are reluctant users of health services;
- integration of mental and physical healthcare at the service team level so that staff become health navigators for their clients;
- the members' level of engagement and education about health conditions, risks, and prevention strategies, so they become active partners in monitoring and maintaining their physical well-being as part of their recovery.

Specific activities of the grant fell into four areas: (1) creating a structure that adapts the CMHC service team function to have a greater focus on the integration of mental and physical healthcare, (2) coordinating strategies to assess physical health issues and risk factors that need attention, (3) creating a system to help individuals access care for their physical health conditions, and (4) continuing support for smoking cessation, exercise, and nutrition classes that increase members' ability to manage their risk and make healthy lifestyle changes.

The grant proposal, not communicated to the Director of Healthcare Management until after the grant was received, proposed a multitude of specific activities including a pilot to identify member's physical health issues and care navigation and coordination activities with one of the CMHC's service teams, which serves approximately 125

members per year. The intended goal was to transfer successful strategies from the pilot program to the larger program, serving more than 500 people per year. The Director of Healthcare Management was tasked as the project director for this grant.

Project Activities

The first project activity the project director focused on was setting up a structure to track health factors associated with treatment and outcomes. This entailed designing a Health Risk and Response Registry (HRRR) for the CMHC's nursing staff and case managers to record risk factors (BMI, obesity, glucose levels, high blood pressure, use of tobacco or substances) and health insurance and provider information. The HRRR was also intended to track the pilot team interventions mutually agreed upon by CMHC case managers and members, such as management of diabetes, assistance with weight loss, assistance with smoking cessation, information about nutrition, etc. To do this, the project director was to train the staff on the pilot team how to utilize the HRRR and incorporate member health needs and goals as a regular part of the case management services. The second project activity required the project director to maintain a list of medical and health-related resources in the community including community health programs and education opportunities for members, such as cholesterol checks, smoking cessations groups, healthy cooking classes, and mobile health vans. The third project activity required the project director to create a companion document titled "My Medical Visit" form for the member and the LVN, team nurse, or case manager to complete on a one-to-one basis. The aim of the form was to help members prepare for upcoming medical appointments by listing the name, address, and directions to the health center or doctor's office, medications, the reason for the visit, and questions the member wanted to

ask during the visit. As part of the efforts to identify members with health risks and health conditions, the LVN helped members monitor and manage health conditions by taking measurements of weight/BMI, blood pressure, glucose levels, and lipid profiles when members came for mental health appointments. She was discussed health promotion topics such as nutrition, healthy eating to manage diabetes or hypertension, exercise, and smoking cessation. To help members navigate the healthcare system, the grant designed a Health Navigation Checklist to use in conjunction with the My Medical Visit form. This Health Navigation Checklist was planned to cover all areas of assistance a client may need to access healthcare, discuss health needs, and follow treatment plans, such as selecting a healthcare provider, making appointments, arranging for transportation, reviewing family history, and filling out paperwork. Lastly, the project director and the LVN were required to identify internal, peer-based, and community-based strategies to help members and prepare a monthly calendar of community health workshops, meetings, support groups, walks, and other healthy opportunities.

The grant amount requested and awarded was \$45,000 for a one-year period from Jan 2014–Dec 2014. The mental health agency noted in the grant application that it sought the support of the grant to allow the project director to concentrate on this project and that the intention was to incorporate this position into the future budget and staffing of the mental health agency after the grant period. The grant amount was budgeted to predominantly cover a portion of the Project Director’s salary (\$39,400), minimal medical supplies, and client support services (\$5,600).

The project director (Director of Healthcare Management) was surprised and concerned about the amount and breadth of deliverable tasks assigned by the grant. After

six months in the position, she was still relatively new to the CMHC, and she had many other job responsibilities in her new and evolving role. Additionally, her reporting structure had become unclear due to the introduction of the new Chief Program Officer. As the DNP program required the DNP student to devote clinical hours to a project designed to improve care in the clinical agency, the DNP student joined the director in her efforts to promote integrated care.

Access to Physical Health Care for People with SMI Grant Implementation

To begin the implementation of the grant titled, *Access to Physical Health Care for People with Serious Mental Illness*, a treatment team consisting of 13 staff members, including the case manager, registered nurse, psychiatrist, Assistant Team Director, and Team Director, was identified as the pilot team of this grant. One existing full-service partnership (FSP) team of approximately 100 members was selected as the pilot group for this aspect of the grant.

Health risk and response registry. The first grant deliverables were to create the HRRR, which the pilot team was to utilize to gather information from the members. The case managers and nurses on the pilot team were trained to gather information, including demographics, insurance information, and the member's modifiable risk factors, from the members on their caseloads. As most mental health workers were unfamiliar with physical health issues and modifiable risk factors, training was provided. The creation of this registry was intended to adapt the existing function of the CMHC's service team to focus more on the integration of mental and physical healthcare by ensuring physical health risk factors, conditions, and treatment were entered into the CMHC's EHR system. The HRRR contained information on demographics and insurance, screening for BMI,

obesity, glucose levels, high blood pressure, high cholesterol, and use of tobacco and/or substances. These specific health indicators and measures were chosen, as they are the modifiable risk factors that impact this population. Ultimately, the envisioned HRRR was not created. However, a revised non-electronic form was created to gather information about members' PCP, insurance status, and some of the modifiable risk factors. Of the 100 members in the pilot group, demographic, insurance and health risk information was gathered from 43 members and entered into the members' records on the EHR.

Training is critical for staff taking on an unfamiliar responsibility. Therefore, in conjunction with the HRRR, the CMHC case managers were to be trained to incorporate physical health planning into members' treatment plans by identifying disease-specific needs and preventive healthcare goals. The case managers were to discuss identified health conditions and risk factors with the member. However, as a result of the staffs' resistance to the HRRR training, subsequent plans and associated training to incorporate physical health planning into member's treatment plans were temporarily abandoned.

Community health resource guide. Another grant deliverable was the creation of a Community Health Resource Guide, containing community health programs and educational opportunities such as mobile health vans, smoking cessation support groups, managing diabetes, controlling high blood pressure, exercise classes, yoga sessions, healthy cooking classes, community PCPs, and insurance information. Along with staff guidance to members, the resource guide aimed to help members manage their chronic physical health conditions in conjunction with their SMI.

The creation of the Community Health Resource Guide was achieved through the collaborative efforts of the nursing staff, nursing students, administrative staff, clerical staff, IT/IS staff, case manager staff, and clinical staff. The rationale for assembling a group for these tasks was to utilize a collaborative interdisciplinary environment to create fully comprehensive tools and resources incorporating various disciplines. The plan was to incorporate the Community Health Resource Guide into the existing intranet system for easy access by staff so they could provide resources to members to support their desired lifestyle changes, encourage member self-management support, and improve members' health.

However, a system-wide server upgrade delayed the addition of the Community Health Resource Guide to the intranet system. This step is now expected to be completed by late spring 2015. The proposed plans for maintaining and updating the Community Health Resource Guide have also been delayed in light of potential organizational reconfigurations and are currently being re-assessed.

My medical visit form. The document named "My Medical Visit" form was created to help members prepare for upcoming medical appointments by listing the name, address, and directions to the health center/doctor's office, the reason for the visit, questions that the member wanted to ask during the visit, and medications. This document was envisioned to improve the physical healthcare appointment experience for members and decrease the anxiety surrounding upcoming medical appointments by having all necessary information and questions in one accessible place that is readily available for their medical visit. This was created in an effort to support members to manage their health status as an empowered and accountable individual. The student

nurses assigned to the agency in a psychiatric-mental health rotation, with oversight from the Director of Healthcare Management and the psychiatric nurse practitioner fine-tuned the format of My Medical Visit form from the existing drafts. The plan was to create and present this new form to staff and members as part of the student nurses' health education teaching project. The student nurses did finalize the format of the form but they did not present the new form to staff or members. The Director of Healthcare Management decided to delay the presentation and training on the form until the staff have been trained on the importance of integrated care for the CMHC members. Therefore, while the My Medical Visit form was created, it has not yet been implemented for staff use.

Barriers—Institutional and Person-Specific

Several barriers to grant implementations and execution were encountered, leading to frequent adjustments of plans and expectations in several areas. One of the first barriers encountered was the restriction of time and resources due to the demands of current roles and responsibilities. For example, the Director of Healthcare Management was expected to devote a significant portion of her responsibilities to achieving and implementing the deliverables of the grant for *Access to Physical Health Care for People with Serious Mental Illness*, determined by the salary contribution from the grant funds. However, this expectation did not align with the reality and constraints of her overall job demands.

Another formidable barrier was the existing EHR system. The goal had been to track health related data in the existing EHR. Ideally, the intention was to create a face sheet for each member that listed their pertinent health information, PCP, and insurance information, which would be easily accessible to each staff member working with any

member. However, the current EHR did not contain insurance information of all the members and was not updated regularly to reflect changes in the members' insurance statuses. This barrier, which was associated with the billing department of the parent mental health agency, could not be overcome. Additionally, restrictions existed in the reconfiguration of the EHR pertaining to what information could be placed on the face sheet template. General health information was not included on the existing face page and could not be added. In addition, many of the desired changes were not included in the EHR vendor contract and, therefore, required additional fees and lengthy waiting periods of several months. Many months were spent attempting to modify, restructure, and reconfigure the existing EHR with minimal to moderate success. Owing to the difficulties encountered by the CMHC with the EHR reconfiguration, the project director decided that the pilot team would collect the required health information on paper and the Director of Healthcare Management would enter it into the EHR.

The pilot team staff, consisting of many long-term employees of the CMHC, had mixed reactions to these additional job responsibilities. Additionally, even though the pilot team had provided care to many long-term members of the CMHC, physical health monitoring had never been a part of the care. The pilot team did not have significant member movement, such as members graduating to lower levels of care or new members being admitted to the team; thus, this sense of stagnation may have contributed to some of the resistance in this part of the project. Some staff were supportive of the new responsibilities, while others showed concern about incorporating these new responsibilities into their existing job requirements, their competency about gathering such information, and the time it would take to gather such information. Some staff felt it

was inappropriate to gather this information, as the agency was a mental health agency, and they did not view this as mental health information. In addition to these challenges, the CMHC leadership or team directors failed to communicate the importance of the CMHC members' physical health and that addressing health issues was now included in the services provided by the CMHC staff.

Owing to the staff's concerns and resistance, the amount of information to collect from the members was reviewed and subsequently reduced. Therefore, the original requirement to collect information on demographics, PCP, insurance status, allergies, current health conditions and medications, and information on six modifiable risks factors (blood pressure, blood glucose, weight/BMI, smoking status, substance use, and exercise) was revised to include the same information on the demographic, PCP, insurance status, allergies, current health conditions, and medication information, but only two modifiable risk factors (smoking status and substance use). Even with these modifications, only 43 of 100 members in the pilot group had this information collected and recorded in their charts.

The resistance from staff brought to light the lack of awareness and support of the grant and its deliverables from the CMHC leadership. The grant had been applied for and delegated by the mental health parent company of the CMHC with few set expectations or plans for implementation. The project director was informed that the grant had been "satisfied" by a report provided by the Chief Development Officer, which seemed to lower and/or eliminate the priority of the grant deliverables (the HRRR, Community Resources Guide, & My Medical Visit form).

The decision was made to delegate the finalization of the Community Health Resource Guide and the My Medical Visit form to the student nurses assigned to the agency in their psychiatric-mental health rotation. The student nurses assembled the Community Health Resource Guide from the large amount of information that had been gathered by various staff at the agency. Once the guide was organized, it was to be posted onto the agency intranet. However, because a server upgrade was still in progress, the Community Health Resource Guide remains in paper form at this time, awaiting electronic posting.

Glimmers of Hope

Despite the barriers and challenges associated with the implementation of the grant, there were also supportive and encouraging signs. One nurse from a team outside of the pilot team expressed her interest and made efforts to track physical health information, PCP information, and insurance information on her assigned members. Supported by the Director of Healthcare Management and the DNP student, the nurse readily used the tools created for the pilot team.

While the EHR barriers were being uncovered and clarified, the opportunity arose for more widespread discussion among the CMHC staff and leadership about the capabilities and constraints of the existing EHR. As the EHR vendor contract was up for renewal in the upcoming year, a sense of hope emerged that the current problems would be addressed in the upcoming contract negotiations. Additionally, the CMHC and the parent mental health agency began discussing the staffs' concerns about the existing EHR.

Ultimately, one of the truest forms of encouragement came from those members who came to see the PCP and received care from him, and from those who were connected with insurance and PCPs in the community. Both the PCP and the LVN established their reputations as approachable, sincere, respectful, helpful, resourceful, and dedicated to helping members, leading to an increased number of members seeing the on-site PCP.

Evolution, More Awareness, and Next Planned Steps

One notable experience that clarified the perspective of some staff members came in the form of questions posed by one of the Team Directors. During a general discussion related to the overall care of the CMHC members, the Team Director inquired about why physical health factors were being addressed. It was found that this Team Director, and hence, probably other staff, lacked knowledge about the disparate physical healthcare received by persons with SMI. In addition, they were unaware of the shortened life spans of those with SMI, resulting from the increased modifiable risk factors, lack of health education, and poor medical care among the seriously mentally ill. The need for generalized information and training about such issues became clear. Plans are being made to provide training to the CMHC staff to raise their level of awareness on the topic and provide the necessary skills to address physical health issues. Training in small team-based settings and general all-staff training are under discussion. Topics to cover include the importance of addressing physical health concerns of members with SMI, a review of the PCP services co-located at the CMHC, and methods of how to refer members to these services.

One area of mixed progress was the My Medical Visit form. The form was drafted and finalized by the Director of Healthcare Management, the DNP student, and the student nurses. However, once the form was completed, it became clear that the information needed to complete and use the form, such as member's insurance status and current health conditions, was not readily available to staff and members. Aligned with the challenges in reconfiguring and using the EHR, basic information about the member's insurance status, PCP, current medications, and health conditions was found to be unavailable to the case managers through the EHR and most members did not know their own information. Therefore, the Director of Healthcare Management made the decision not to implement this form at this time. Instead, efforts to improve and reconfigure the EHR will continue to make the information necessary for use of this form readily available to staff. Additionally, a plan has been made to secure the support of CMHC leadership and provide training on integrated care and the new roles and forms associated with providing integrated care.

As the end of the *Integrated Healthcare Project* grant approached, clarity was needed on whether the on-site embedded PCP and LVN could be retained for ongoing service. The parent mental health agency, which had been searching for new grants to continue this service, then announced that funds had been secured through a Boeing grant that would support the PCP to continue his service for approximately 9–12 months. The LVN could be absorbed into the CMHC budget by combining an unfilled position for a medical assistant and a portion of an existing staff nurse position. The funding arrangements in both cases were made possible by the parent mental health agency of the CMHC.

Data Management

The CEO of the parent mental health agency requested that the Director of Healthcare Management apply to present the *Integrated Healthcare Project* data and information at the Psychosocial Rehabilitation Association Annual Conference. As a result of this request, the data captured during the grant needed to be evaluated. The Director of Healthcare Management approached the DNP student to assist in the analysis and presentation of the data. In support of the fullest sense of integration and to present different perspectives of the grant project and outcomes, the PCP and LVN were invited to participate in the conference preparation and presentation. The Director of Healthcare Management, the DNP student, PCP, and LVN submitted an abstract of the paper to present at the conference. The submission was accepted and will be presented in June 2015, thus confirming the need to evaluate the data associated with this grant.

A data analysis of the information gathered during *the Integrated Healthcare Project* was performed by the DNP student using Excel pivot tables and cross-tabulations. Despite the CEO's request for the data to be presented and the staff's eagerness to do so, the information and awareness of this data was still exceptionally limited. The leadership of the CMHC remained largely unaware of the specifics of the grant efforts, the data that was being gathered and analyzed, and the efforts to find funding to continue the services. Consequently, it was decided that the data analysis, as well as particular member experiences and situations from the first year of the *Integrated Healthcare Project*, would be shared with CMHC staff, leadership staff, and the leadership of the parent mental health agency to highlight the impact of the PCP's services.

The grant initiatives and implementation efforts raised awareness of the lack of standardized health monitoring schemes, the lack of policies and protocols to guide this care, and the lack of adherence to overarching county policies related to physical healthcare monitoring. This awareness led to discussion among the Chief Program Officer, the Director of Healthcare Management, and the DNP student, which resulted in the creation of a plan for new initiatives. Policies and procedures for physical healthcare monitoring will be developed and staff training on these policies and procedures will be conducted. There is now an awareness and discussion about the CMHC's cultural resistance to policies and procedures. Use of policies and procedures is seen by many in the agency as a method that conflicts with, derails, and prevents the provision of individualized psychosocial rehabilitation upon which the CMHC prides itself.

Currently, there is also discussion and support for a Chief Nursing Officer (CNO) to be added to the senior management of the parent mental health agency as well as a Director of Nursing (DON), also located at the parent mental health agency, who will focus on creating standardization among all clinical programs of the parent mental health agency. The CNO and DON will be charged with overseeing the implementation of integrated care grants and establishing agency-wide continuous quality improvement for these, and other, programs.

Discussions are currently being held about the feasibility of applying for a new grant to support further integrated care efforts. The Chief Program Officer, the Director of Healthcare Management, and the DNP student are evaluating the agency's ability to implement this grant with the CMHC leadership, including the Medical Director and the Chief Development Officer, Chief Administrative Officer, Chief Operating Officer, and

Chief Executive Officer from the parent mental health agency. These group discussions and coordinated efforts appear to symbolize a more collaborative, cohesive, and focused effort by the parent mental health agency and the CMHC to extend the provision of integrated care.

There are also plans to shift the intended pilot team activities from the *Access to Physical Health Care for People with Serious Mental Illness* grant to another service team, which would serve as an entry point for many new members. This team is one of two teams that recently prioritized adding a nurse to their team. The team and the nurse both have an awareness and interest in addressing the physical healthcare of the members they serve. The combination of new members and interest in physical care make the team ripe for establishing new methods of integrated care.

Results

In the *Integrated Healthcare Project* grant, 159 unduplicated members were treated by the on-site PCP physician and nurse, exceeding the expected outcome of 125 members to be treated by the on-site PCP. At the end of the grant period, 79 members had been connected or re-connected with health insurance. However, this failed to meet the grant expectation of connecting or re-connecting 100 members with health insurance. By the end of the grant period, 76 members had either been connected to a PCP in the community, had a first visit with a community PCP, or identified a community PCP. However, this also failed to meet the grant criteria set forth of having 125 members identify or connect with a community PCP.

Regarding the grant for *Access to Physical Health Care for People with Serious Mental Illness*, of the 100 members in the pilot group, health risk information of 43

members was gathered and entered into their charts. While there were significant and notable shifts in culture and increased organizational awareness at the end of the grant period, the specified grant deliverables were not achieved.

Discussion

General lessons and themes can be learned from this case study. One such lesson is the importance of cohesive and proactive planning. Additionally, it is clear that the vision underpinning implementation must be a shared vision among leadership and staff. This vision must be communicated clearly and passionately to those who are required to support the logistics of achieving the vision. The constraints of limited resources, while a reality, must be creatively challenged and managed as well as realistically understood. Lastly, culture shift and organizational change requires time, a steadfast and clear vision, and a level of flexibility and adaptation. Role shifts and the resetting of organizational priorities are necessary elements in constructing and establishing the envisioned systems to provide integrated care.

APPENDIX B**LETTER OF PERMISSION FROM CMHC**

November 12, 2014

Mental Health America Los Angeles
100 W. Broadway, Suite 5010
Long Beach, CA 90802

To Whom It May Concern,

Mental Health America Los Angeles (MHA) grants Ms. Kathleen M. McDermott permission to use all de-identified data associated with the Integrated Healthcare Project grant provided by the California Community Foundation and conducted at MHA Village in completing her doctoral project and any publications or presentations resulting from the project. However, MHA will require its approval of any publications in which the agency is identified by name. The data generated by the project are a retrospective compilation of interventions accomplished during the course of grant activities for a report to the funding body and the agency does not consider it to be human subjects research.

Sincerely,

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Dave Pilon', is written over a light blue horizontal line.

Dave Pilon, Ph.D.
President and CEO

www.mhala.org

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APPENDIX C

CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY LOS ANGELES
INSTITUTIONAL REVIEW BOARD WAIVER**Office Memorandum**

DATE: December 16, 2014

TO: Paula K. Vuckovich and Kathleen McDermott
Nursing, NSS

FROM: E. Amaro, Institutional Review Board – Human Subjects

COPIES TO: S. Ulanoff, Chair; J. Shiotsugu, Executive Secretary

SUBJECT: Review of Project Involving Human Subjects

Applicant: Paula K. Vuckovich and Kathleen McDermott

Title: Integrating Physical Health Care in a Community Mental Health Center for
Persons with Serious Mental Illness

Application #: IRB W14-1

Date of Review: December 9, 2014

Action: Approved 12/16/14
 Convened committee
 Expedited (reviewed and approved by IRB chair or designee)
 Denied - see below
 Tabled - see below
 Administrative Action Waiver
 Informed Consent:

APPENDIX D

LEVELS OF COLLABORATION/INTEGRATION

(adapted from SAMHSA Six Levels of Collaboration/Integration, Tables 1–3)

COORDINATED Key element—Communication		CO-LOCATED Key element—Physical Proximity		INTEGRATED Key element—Practice Change	
Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5	Level 6
Minimal Collaboration	Basic Collaboration (at a distance)	Basic Collaboration (onsite)	Close Collaboration (onsite, some system integration)	Close Collaboration (almost integrated)	Full Collaboration (merged integrated practice)
Separate facilities	Separate facilities	Same facility, not necessarily the same offices	Same space within the same facility	Same space within the same facility (some shared space)	Same space within the same facility (sharing all practice space)
Separate systems	Separate systems	Separate systems	Some shared systems	Seeking system solutions together	One integrated system
Rare communication (no face to face)	Periodic communication, may have larger team meetings	Regular communication, meet occasionally	Communicate in person as needed, regular in person interactions	Frequent communication in person, regular team meetings	Consistent communication at system, team, and individual levels
Separate treatment plans	Separate treatment plans	Separate service plans with some shared information	Collaborative treatment planning for specific patients	Collaborative treatment planning for all shared patients	One treatment plan for all patients
Evidence-based practices (EBPs) utilized separately	Separate EBPs	Some shared knowledge of each other's EBPs	Some shared EBPs and some shared trainings	EBPs shared across systems, joint monitoring of health conditions for some patients	EBPs are team selected, trained, and implemented across disciplines as a standard practice
Patient physical health and behavioral health needs treated as separate issues	Patient health needs treated separately but records are shared	Patient health needs treated separately at the same location	Patient needs are treated separately at the same site, may have collaborative gestures	Patient needs are treated as a team for shared patients and separately for non-shared patients	Patient health needs for all patients are treated by a team, who function effectively together

